

Identification of Student Administration at SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli, North Sumatra

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to identify the student administration system, assess the efficiency of software usage, and identify challenges faced by SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli in managing student data, particularly in the context of new student admissions. The research method used is a qualitative approach with a case study as the framework. The results show that the student administration system in the school has progressed, especially in the use of software to manage data. However, there are challenges in the admission of new students involving complex administrative processes. The efficiency of using software to manage student data requires improvement, although it has positively contributed to facilitating administrative tasks. The main challenges involve better data integration, staff training needed to operate the software effectively, and improved coordination among units in the school. The findings of this research provide valuable insights for researchers, as well as for SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli in developing a more efficient and effective student administration, especially in the context of new student admissions and student data management

INTRODUCTION

The administration of students is an integral part of educational institution management that has direct implications for the quality and effectiveness of education. In the era of globalization and rapid social changes, student administration faces various challenges that require in-depth understanding and appropriate solutions. Some factors supporting the importance of research and better understanding of student administration include:

1. **Paradigm Shift in Education:**** Current education is no longer solely focused on knowledge transfer but also on the development of skills and character. This places new demands on student administration to facilitate outcome-oriented learning.
2. **Diversification of Student Body:**** Schools today have students with diverse backgrounds, abilities, and needs. Student administration must be able to accommodate this diversity and ensure that all students receive education tailored to their needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research aims to describe how the administration system works in the admission of new students at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli. It also aims to describe the use of software that can influence the efficiency of student administration at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli. Furthermore, it seeks to identify the challenges faced in managing student administration at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli. Therefore, research on student administration is conducted to address these aspects

METHODOLOGY

The research method used by the researcher is a qualitative method with a descriptive case study format. A case study is a comprehensive investigation of an individual or a group of individuals as a case to provide an accurate and complete description (Marczyk, DeMatteo & Festinger, 2005: 147). The research population consists of administrative staff and students of SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli.

To obtain data related to the research topic, the researcher conducted direct interviews with informants. The research technique used by the researcher is observation and note-taking, where after obtaining information from the informants, the researcher observes, takes notes, and summarizes the information provided by the informants.

RESULT

Here is the translation of the text:

Findings from the research are as follows:

a. Administration System in the Admission of New Students at SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli:

The current information administration system has a significant influence, particularly in the process of admitting new students to the school. One area that has developed in information technology is Data Processing Techniques, which is applied in various institutions such as government agencies, schools, hospitals, and others.

In the field of education, data processing techniques are applied in the Department of Education and public schools, including processing student attendance data, teacher data, school library book data, and more.

At SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli, one of the high schools in Deli Serdang Regency, data processing has been maximized using an information administration system, especially in the provision of information. Data processing utilizes an Online New Student Admission System (PPDB) where the registration of new students is done by filling out forms independently using the devices of the students who wish to register. The data is then recorded on the PPDB website, which collaborates with the school. After the data is recorded, it is transferred to a computer using Microsoft Excel by school administrative staff, speeding up the necessary data processing. The data of each new student is entered into the student database online after a few days of processing.

b. Use of Software that Can Affect the Efficiency of Student Administration at SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli:

The use of information and communication technology has permeated every aspect of daily life in the current digital era. Utilizing a website is one way to leverage this technology, and it can be a useful tool in the educational environment for the New Student Admission Process (PPDB) at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli.

Traditional PPDB processes without information technology involvement have their own issues. One major problem is the complex and time-consuming administrative handling (Ramadhani, Rushainy, Mufit, Erlangga, & Nst, 2022). Manual processes involve collecting physical documents, manually filling out forms, and manually verifying and checking data. This can consume significant time and energy for the school. Additionally, manual PPDB processes pose a higher risk of human errors, such as data entry mistakes or document loss. These errors can affect fairness and objectivity in the student selection process.

A website is a software used by school staff, which is a collection of interconnected web pages accessible through the internet. The website is used to present information, allowing visitors to access information or content anytime and anywhere. With a website, information can be accessed online, whether through a desktop computer, laptop, tablet, or other mobile devices. This provides flexibility for visitors to obtain the information they need without being restricted by time or location.

c. Challenges Faced in Managing Student Administration at SMA N 1 Labuhan Deli:

The curriculum is one of the key components of education that plays a crucial role in determining the direction in which the goals and objectives of students will be taken, as well as the minimum skills and expertise students should possess after completing the education program. Therefore, managing the curriculum and learning activities is not exempt from various challenges that demand specific adjustments in the field of education.

One challenge in curriculum management at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli is the constant changes in the curriculum over time. It is often said that Indonesia is a country that frequently changes and modifies the curriculum, leading to the notion that every change in ministerial leadership results in a change in the curriculum. The frequent changes and modifications in the curriculum, based on policy and not supported by a systematic feasibility study, can confuse teachers and create problems.

Current education faces fundamental issues due to the frequent change of leadership, with each change of leadership bringing about changes, especially in education policies and curricula that may not be relevant to student needs. Issues include an excessive number of subjects, a heavy workload, and unclear orientation. There may be many challenges faced by the school staff, but due to time and opportunity constraints, the information obtained by the researcher is limited to this.

DISCUSSION

In the presented research findings, there are several crucial points that need to be considered in the discussion. First, SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli has successfully implemented a sophisticated information administration system in the new student admission process. The online registration process through the PPDB application has positively impacted data processing, making it faster. However, it is important to consider the effectiveness of this system and the extent to which all parties involved (students, parents, and administrative staff) participate in accessing and using the system effectively.

Second, the use of software and information technology in the educational administration process is a significant development. Utilizing a website and software provides easy access to information and flexibility for users to obtain data anytime, anywhere. However, it should be discussed whether the administrative staff has received adequate training to manage this software and whether steps have been taken to ensure the security of student data and privacy protection.

Finally, the challenges in curriculum management identified in this research reflect common issues in the world of education. Frequent and sometimes poorly coordinated changes in the curriculum can pose difficulties for teachers and disrupt the teaching and learning process. The discussion of these research findings should include considerations of how continuous curriculum changes can affect the quality of education and what efforts schools can make to address these challenges.

Overall, this research illustrates the complexity of student administration at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli and the efforts made to improve efficiency through information technology. The discussion emphasizes the need for careful planning and training in implementing such technology, while also highlighting the importance of ongoing curriculum changes to enhance the quality of education

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The administration system for new student admissions at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli has successfully leveraged information technology, particularly in data processing and new student registration. This process has effectively integrated technology, starting from online form submission to data processing by administrative staff. The rules of the new student registration information system have been well-designed to ensure that the process runs efficiently and transparently.

The use of software in the form of a website has also contributed to improving the efficiency of student administration at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli. This website enables online access to information, reducing the complexity and time-consuming administrative burdens in the new student admission process. With the website in place, prospective students and parents can easily access the information they need, including registration data, payments, and admission status.

However, there are still challenges in managing student administration at this school. One of them is the frequent curriculum changes, which can confuse teachers and students and require continuous adjustments. Additionally, leadership changes and education policies that may not always align with students' needs pose challenges that need to be addressed.

Overall, the use of information technology and software has brought many benefits to educational administration at SMAN 1 Labuhan Deli. However, efforts are still required to address the existing challenges so that educational management can operate more effectively and efficiently.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Identification of Student Administration in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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